

Building Context-Rich Mobile Cloud Services for Mobile Cloud Applications

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Abstract: Today's mobile applications require more computational by intensive capabilities such as natural language processing, computer vision and graphics, machine learning etc. These demands cannot be met just by production of more powerful mobile devices. Therefore, mobile applications will have to become more personalized, context aware, and able to recognize not only the location of the user, but also their cognitive preferences. To support these demands, the future mobile computing applications will be built in environments that provide a set of context-rich support services. These applications will leverage the mobile and cloud computing technology in order to deliver mobile cloud applications or mCloud applications. Developers will use these context-rich support services as building blocks to realize a large class of basic mobile cloud services or mCloud services in short. Therefore, the main contribution of this paper is to propose a model of context-rich mCloud services that can support the development of mobile cloud applications. The proposed model will be verified by many use cases identifying the most appropriate services to generate custom-made multimedia output. The essence of the proposed model will consider the different aspects and influencing factors that are part of the Quality of Experience (QoE) process and metrics.

Keywords: mobile cloud applications, context-rich services, mobile cloud services, data mining

1. Introduction

The increased popularity of mobile devices has led to immense development of mobile applications, in particular social networking applications. In parallel to this trend, the mobile devices are becoming more technically sophisticated. They are able to produce and play multimedia content; they have bigger displays; they possess sensor technology, like accelerometers to detect the orientation of the device, Global Positioning System (GPS) capabilities and gyroscopic sensors for navigation. Inserting all of this technology into a mobile device makes it a perfect instrument for social media networking, electronic payment, distance learning, micro blogs and etc. In order to stimulate fast growth of mobile applications there have been created mobile versions of the existing web based social networking sites. Therefore, mobile applications should offer personalization, context-awareness, not only by providing the location of the user, but by supplying information that matches user cognitive preferences. In order to deliver these requirements the mobile cloud computing technology paradigm was introduced. Mobile cloud computing is a model for transparent elastic augmentation of mobile device working capabilities (Kader et al. 2014). Computation has been transformed in a model consisting of a set of services that can be reused and delivered in a manner similar to utilities, such as water, electricity.

The existing basic mobile services such as communication service, short message service and location detection service will be extended to mobile cloud (mCloud) services. These services consider the use of cloud-based data mining algorithms to be applied on large scale data. A typical example is to run an analysis of a large group of people on a social media network, in order to extract collective ratings or trends in real time. The newly proposed service will need to consider the context-aware conditions, collective group ratings and users personal preferences. In fact, this aspects confirm with the concept of Quality of Experience (QoE), which is generally defined as the degree of delight or annoyance of a person whose experiencing involves an application, service, or system (Raake and Egger 2014). Therefore, the process of building the context-rich mCloud services will need to consider the different aspects previously mentioned.

The main research hypothesis in this paper is: Mobile cloud applications provide users with personalized and context-aware information by using context-rich mCloud services. These services are responsible for running the analysis on large scale data and deliver the aggregated data back to the mobile user.

The paper is structured as follows. Firstly, it provides an overview of the relevant literature. Subsequently, in section three is described the cloud computing framework for context-rich mCloud services. In the fourth section

is shown the process of building context-rich mCloud services. In section five is described use case of mCloud application. The final section discusses the main conclusions and further research paths.

2. Literature review

The emergence of hybrid mobile application development platforms allowed programmers to develop mobile applications that can be used for different types of mobile devices (Nagesh and Caicedo 2012). These platforms are using web-based technologies to design nice user interfaces and native shells to access mobile native functionality (Singh 2013). One of the first applications based on hybrid mobile application technology was created using mobile development framework PhoneGap, which uses HTML5, CSS3, and JavaScript technology. The main benefit of using the hybrid mobile application development platforms is that it uses HTML5 and JavaScript native containers to access the mobile device built-in features. In this way it is easy to create mobile applications that use mobile native features, such as camera, Global Positioning System (GPS) and other sensors and that can be deployed on different mobile device models (Android, iOS, Windows and etc.). Recently much research focused on lightweight applications that are written in a high level markup and scripting language, providing improved cross platform support and using a container for hybrid applications (Jaramillo et al. 2013). The advantage of the proposed concept by Jaramillo et al. is the reduced development lifecycle time and a consistent application security model within large organizations. Some of the existing methodologies are proposing a remote assessment platform that records context in user properties and user interactions with the mobile device (Pretel and Lago 2014), which are important to evaluate the user experience. This research goes beyond this trend of hybrid mobile applications and proposes mCloud applications that will deliver services based on cloud computing technology.

The cloud computing concept can be understood as a technology where total computing can be achieved by using a remote network where owners of hardware and soft resources are external parties. In fact, the computation offloading technique is been used, in order to migrate the large computations and complex processing from mobile devices to resourceful machines (Kader et al, 2014). This led to inaugurate the mCloud computing paradigm for users to access and receive data from the cloud, and it is a rapid method for accessing cloud computing resources effectively by using mobile devices. Today there are many mobile devices with different operating systems that are running on the limited set of formats (H.264, MPEG-4) and they support different codec (Hossain 2014). Hossain's research suggests that suitable services based on selected Quality of Service parameters should be used, in order to increase user's satisfaction with the delivered multimedia content.

Personalizing the information that should be delivered to the end user of mobile application has always been a research challenge. In order to deliver personalized recommendations for cloud services it was proposed recommendation algorithm based on usage history and combined relationship of cloud services (Zhang et al. 2013). Another important point that needs to be considered is the *interest* as individual experience in the social media sites. The social media sites provide the users with large amounts of content, from which it is difficult to extract the information that is of user interest. This requires capitalizing the cloud computing infrastructure to discover and manage social media content through services that perform analytics on a large scale (Zelenkauskaitė and Simões 2014). This approach motivated improved models of context-rich mCloud services that can support the development of mCloud applications.

The service architecture based on the concept of cloud computing has functioned as an essential element to ensure the access and processing of inhomogeneous data. This type of data is commonly found in social networking sites where the number of users and posted media items is growing exponentially. Therefore, the social-based recommendation systems recently have attracted substantial interest in research where system predictions are made based on users interests (Hsiao et al. 2014). Hsiao et al. (2014) have already proposed a model for collaborative retrieval, and proven that it outperforms the existing approaches by incorporating relevant information from social networks. The personalization in social recommendation models have been improved by introducing two common factors, category and keyword, besides the social information in the process of prediction making (Ji and Shen 2014). The performance of recommendation systems was improved by using so-called hybrid recommendation algorithms, which were designed for parallel execution on Map/Reduce framework (Kunhui et al. 2014). This and similar research have inspired us to propose the context-rich (mCloud) services that run on top of cloud computing framework.

3. Cloud computing framework for context-rich mCloud services

Cloud computing brings many benefits and useful applications for mobile users and service providers. Offloading of resource intensive computations to the mCloud allows mobile applications to provide users with much richer services in terms of data size, faster processing speed and longer battery time (Verma and Rastogi 2014). The cloud computing services are hierarchically built from bottom to top in the order of Infrastructure, platform and software service (Ahmed and Hossain 2014). The layered framework proposed by Thuraisingham (2013) is generally used for applications for social networking, insider treat analysis, malware detection and ontology management. The previously mentioned applications are resource and computational intensive. Therefore, the proposed model of context-rich mCloud services will support the development of mCloud applications that are created on the base of a cloud computing framework.

The basis of the framework is the storage and infrastructure layer, see Figure 1. This layer consists of the HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File System) infrastructure data cluster file system that stores, processes, retrieves and manages data. The HDFS is the basis for the widely known parallel processing model MapReduce, which consists of master and slave nodes (Xie et al. 2010). The master node controls a group of slave nodes on which the Map and Reduce functions run in parallel (Xie et al. 2010). The main advantage of MapReduce model is that allows systems to run on a set of homogeneous nodes including both computing and storage nodes, located in the infrastructure layer. On the foundations of this layer is build the second layer for cloud operating system (OS) and hypervisor layer. This layer carries out the virtualization, as well the memory management, scheduling and interposes communication management (Thuraisingham 2013).

For the proposed model of context-rich mCloud services the main role is played by the next layer in the proposed framework, i.e. is the cloud platform layer, which holds the data mining platform and database management system. On top of the cloud computing framework for context-rich mCloud services is the cloud application layer. This layer integrates all of the mCloud services, such as location-based service, data mining service, entertainment and weather service, see Figure 1. These mCloud services are responsible for the communication between mobile device and the mCloud.

Figure 1: Cloud computing framework

The proposed cloud framework for context-rich mCloud services aims at transforming the social media generated content, stored in the infrastructure layer, into useful information that is relevant to the end user. The third – cloud platform layer has the role of intelligent engine that should support appropriate algorithms to provide the application layer with aggregated information.

4. Context-rich mobile cloud services

The social media has been primarily considered as a source of additional revenue, by providing new meaningful insights from proprietary data and solve complex problems that so far were impossible to address (Higdon et al. 2013). The complexity and diversity of this data is a major research challenge in the process to unlock the hidden

knowledge. In this research the focus is put on extracting the most relevant information, from social network sites, that is of user's interest in context-aware conditions.

The existing social networking sites, such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Google+ and etc., do simple aggregation of the most popular media content. Based on this popularity and previous users interests the most recent media contents are been recommended to the users. But these recommendations do not consider the context-aware user needs; they only depend on the aggregate activity of a lot of other users. Very popular types of recommendation are those tailored to the individual users. Typical examples are book recommendations tailored to users taste, or movie recommendations based on movies that the user has watched previously.

Some of the most common problems that recommendation systems are facing are (Rajaraman and Ullman 2011):

- Cold start or not having gathered the known ratings.
- The second problem is how to extrapolate unknown ratings from known ratings. Here we are mainly interested in the high unknown ratings. In example, we are interested in those ratings where a user would have given a high rating to a movie, not the average or the low ratings.
- The third key problem is evaluating extrapolation methods. Once we have a recommendation system that can extrapolate unknown ratings from known ratings and because we do not know if the recommended system is doing well, this is where evaluation methodologies come in.

The first and simplest way of gathering ratings is what is called explicit patterns, or asking people to rate items. This method is good because we are asking people to directly rate items and we can decide on what scale people are going to rate items. For example, we can ask for ratings on a one to five star scale, we can ask people to rate on a scale from zero to ten, or we can just ask people to say whether they like an item or did not like it. The explicit method has the advantage of simplicity and of getting direct responses from users. The problem, though, is that it does not scale. Only a small fraction of users who viewed a movie, listened to a piece of music or bought a product actually bothers to leave a rating or review. Most users do not actually leave ratings or reviews.

So while data that are explicitly gathered are excellent data, it is not sufficient in most cases for recommendations. Since explicit ratings do not scale, a lot of sites use implicit ratings. The idea behind implicit ratings is to learn ratings from other user actions. For example an online shopping website might have a rule that a purchase implies a high rating. Now the nice thing about implicit ratings is that they are much more scalable than explicit ratings. Because the user does not have to explicitly rate an item, and there are way more other actions than there are ratings. The problem though is that it is very hard using implicit ratings to learn low ratings. It is quite easy to learn high ratings because we might have a rule that a purchase might imply the high rating. But we can never learn a rating that a user disliked a product implicitly.

The key problem of extrapolating utilities is that the matrix U , the utility matrix is very sparse. Most people have not rated most items and this introduces a slew of problems. The second problem that we have is a cold start problem. When we have a new item or a new user, the new item does not have any ratings, and new users have no history. There is one efficient approach to building recommendation systems by using the content-based recommendations (Rajaraman and Ullman 2011).

4.1 Recommendation algorithms

The main idea behind content-based recommendation systems is to recommend items to a customer x similar to previous items rated highly by the same customer. For example, in movies we might recommend movies with the same actor(s), director, and genre and etc. In the case of websites, blogs or news, we might recommend articles with similar content or similar topics. In the case of people recommendations, we might recommend people with many common friends. We are going to start with a user and find out a set of items the user likes using both explicit and implicit data. For example, we might look at the items that the user has rated highly and the set of items the user has purchased. And for each of those items, we are going to build an item profile. An item profile is a description of the item. Now that we have item profile, our next task is to construct user profile. Let's say we have a user who has rated items with profiles i_1 through i_n . These are vectors in a high dimensional space. The simplest way to construct a user profile from a set of item profiles is just to average the item profiles.

Where n is the total number of item profiles. So if we take all the item profiles from the users, all the items the user has rated and then take the average, would be the simplest way of constructing a user profile.

The best thing of the content-based recommendation approach is that we do not need data about other users in order to make recommendations to a specific user. This is positive thing because we can start making content-based recommendations from day one for the very first user. Another good thing about content-based recommendation is that it can recommend to users a very unique taste. The content-based approach is able to deal marginally with the fact the users can have unique tastes as long as we can build item profiles for the items that the user likes first. Third thing is that we are able to recommend new and unpopular items. Now when a new item comes in we do not need any ratings from users to build the item profile. The item profile depends entirely on the features of the items and not on how other users rated the item so we do not have a so called first-rating problem. Therefore, we can make recommendation for item as soon as it becomes available.

4.2 Implementation of recommendation algorithm as map/reduce job

Considering that our intention is to use the content-based recommendation system by exploiting the cloud services. We have proposed to be used the following implementation of recommendation algorithm as Map/Reduce job.

The content based similarity module analyses the content of a content-based similarity recommendation service. The similarity can be calculated using the dice coefficient, jaccard coefficient or hamming distance. Usually we calculate the content-based similarity for recommendation data sets that consists of the three columns:

- First column: userid
- Second columns: item
- Third column: rating

The content-based recommendation similarity is implemented in Map/Reduce job and the process is as follows:

Step 1 Map/Reduce: The input data file is processed using the unique key values as parameters. The Mapper is grouping the values by the column's unique key values. The Reducer rearranges the values for the similarity / distance analysis, and returns column with unique key value received by the i -th iteration value set.

Step 2 Map/Reduce: The Mapper is rearranging the values and prepares them for the conditional similarity / distance calculation. The Reducer returns the column with unique key value received by the i -th iteration value set with the result for each calculation.

The cloud-based service platform for running the content-based recommendation similarity is done in Ankus - Open Source Big Data Mining Platform (Ren et al. 2014).

At this point we raise the following question: is it possible to make proper recommendation of media content by simply analysing the social network behaviour of the users? Yes, but in the same time we need to consider firstly the users interest and secondly the context-aware conditions of the end user. User's interest can be observed by using search tool and historical analysis on log data, which is not the focus of this research. While, the context-aware conditions of the user can be easily observed by analysis of sensor data from a mobile device. These smart devices can reveal the location of the mobile user. Also, they store camera images and videos, a personal list of contacts that can be linked with the profiles on most common social network sites. These mobile sensor data can be very useful in the process of building customized context-rich information that is from user's interest.

The proposed context-rich mCloud services are responsible for gathering more relevant information from the mobile user to be able to build users profile. Some of these mCloud services require data mining analysis of the user's social networking data and mobile sensor data to be run, in order to extract cognitive clues relevant to the user. The cloud-based data mining services need to scale from the large data sets the services that should extract the user important social behaviour information. The process of building of new service oriented model requires mobile devices as service providers to build a sensing-based application platform. This platform is

responsible for gathering all context related information, such as mobile device type, supported media formats, codecs, location of the user and etc. With proper selection of mCloud services we will be able to deliver the mobile users with personalized and context-aware information in form of mCloud application.

Figure 2: Demonstration of using the cloud-based services for data mining analysis

5. Mobile cloud applications

Context-rich systems have to make intelligent decisions in the process of delivery of information. Another important feature of these systems is the ability to understand the users and respond appropriately to their requests. With the development of mobile applications location-based service is now widely used and location-based mobile search has become a research topic. However, traditional location-based mobile search technology could only provide homogeneous results to different users, rather than distinctive results depending on different personal preferences. This paper introduces a model of context-rich mCloud services that can support the development of mCloud applications. By using an improved data mining algorithm, we can get the content-based recommendation results that are closer to users' preferences.

5.1 Location-based recommendation

The use case example demonstrates a personalized restaurant search in mCloud Social Network Application on smart phone. The mCloud application is like any other social networks, it has news feed, list of friends, part for private messaging and social network rating notification. The new feature is the context-rich personalized recommendation stream, represented with the blue arrow in the right top corner in Figure 3. The initial phase of the stream is to collect information, starting with the term of user's interest. Then using the mobile device GPS sensors is possible to determine the user's locations. Also, it records the current date and time of the user's request. Then comes the second phase where it calls the data mining mCloud services in order to extract relevant results from user's friends and social network ratings. Now we have considered that this request should deliver recommendation for *location*. The results that are presented to the user are shown in the centre of the mCloud application and are rated based on these priorities:

- *Social network rating*, which is extracted based on rating of all member of the social network;
- *Friend's previous experience* for the term of interest;
- *Location-based service* that determines the user's position;
- The current *date and time*, which is relevant to determine if the recommended location is open at the moment;

In this use case the focus of user's interest is to find the best place that serves "Italian pasta" in centre of city Skopje. The output results give detail information for: the name of the restaurant, distance from user's location, average social network rating and average friend's preference rating. This way, the user has been provided with list of context-rich aggregated information from its point of interest.

Figure 3: mCloud social network application (location-based search)

5.2 Interest-based recommendation

The second use case example demonstrates an interest-based search in mCloud Social Network Application on smart phone. Similarly, the process starts by gathering information that is of interest to the user. Considering that the focus in this case is the *interest* for a particular topic, the location-based services are not needed. The current date and time of the user’s request are required because information has to be up-to-date. The recommendation is based on data mining mCloud services from user’s friends and social network ratings. Presented results that are shown in the centre of the mCloud application are rated based on these priorities:

- *Social network rating*, which is extracted based on rating of all member of the social network;
- *Friend’s preference rating* related to the term of interest;
- The current *date and time*, which is relevant to determine the newest information;

The main focus of user’s interest, in this use case, is to find the most relevant information for the topic “watch on eBay” (see Figure 4). The information that the user is looking for is related to purchasing the item watch from the online shopping site eBay. In fact, the user is not interested in the price of the watch on the site eBay rather his interest is whether it is convenient for him to buy that item from that site at the moment. The output results give information details on: the popular relevant information, how old is the information, average social network rating and average friend’s preference rating.

Figure 4: mCloud social network application (interest-based search)

The case study has confirmed mCloud applications provide users with personalized and context-aware information by exhausting the context-rich mCloud services. These proposed applications face privacy risk, because they collect records of user's location and time. The main issue is that this information is sent to remote storage location for processing. This procedure raises security issues, because there is a possible risk of exposing user's data by an unreliable third party mobile cloud service vendor. The risks are expected to be overcome with the introduction of standardization in the field of cloud computing technology.

6. Conclusion

Mobility brings many ubiquitous features, which necessitate the introduction of context-rich mCloud services. These services will gather relevant information from mobile device's sensors, user's data, and network status. Using central intelligent mCloud, the services can handle filtration and aggregation of social media data. In order for mCloud social networking application to provide the users with relevant contextual information and depending of the user requests different mCloud services are used to extract the user important social behaviour information.. Therefore, the development process of mCloud applications will be simplified, because of the cloud based services. User interactivity time with the mCloud social networking application is decreased, because the large computations of complex processing of data sets are done in the cloud. Based on the user's context-aware preferences the mCloud application is able to personalize the delivered media content. Ultimately, this research provides analysis of the key QoE influencing factors that affect the process and metrics for mCloud applications.

Further research is needed to expand the number of context-rich mCloud services that will be relevant for mCloud social networking applications. As the process of standardization of cloud computing technology will become established the process of building context-rich mCloud services will be improved.

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